

COMBINED HARVESTING OF CHAFF AND STRAW FOR BIOETHANOL PRODUCTION: THE FIRST EXPERIENCE ON WHEAT IN SWEDEN

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this work is the evaluation of a harvest chain aimed at incorporating the chaff into the straw bales as consequence of wheat harvest operation. The test was performed in August 2017 in Uppsala, Sweden, using a commercial hybrid combine harvester equipped with a modified chaff spreader and a tractor with round baler. In particular, the chaff spreader was used as chaff recovery system to redirect the chaff into the straw flow during its fall on the ground and get the product admixed in the straw swath. The combine was also used with the recovery systems in "spreading mode" to be experimented as control. A few companies are approaching this engineering challenge, however, as the market of agricultural residues for fuel production is growing, simple and affordable solutions should be identified and commercialized. This paper can be considered as a primary attempt to find a simplified and affordable solution in this direction. The results show different harvesting performances according to machine settings. Indeed, when the recovery system was used, the material falling into the swath and baled was about 340 kg (14%) higher per ha (dry basis). However, respect the amount of biomass potentially available for baling, high harvest losses were identified and indicated the need to repeat the test with other machineries and find further adjustments.

Keywords: agricultural residues, biomass, bioethanol, mechanization

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, the agro-food sector produces large quantities of residues deriving from field operations and processing of raw material. In many cases, these products are considered a waste to be disposed rather than a resource, but in reality they could be addressed according to type and quantity to different bio-energy production chains such as the anaerobic digestion, the combustion and the bioethanol production [1].

The pros and cons of using agricultural residue as energy source instead of other purposes have been broadly studied in the past years [2-6]. Scientific debates apart, the agricultural sector would be capable to furnish large quantity of these by-products if efficient and affordable systems for their recovery and pre-processing would be identified.

Within the categories of by-products deriving from the agricultural sector, the most common receiving higher attention nowadays are the pruning, the cereal straw, and the fruits hulls and kernels deriving from industrial cultivations [7].

However, in the last years, a growing interest in the production of energy also from "minor" residues are taking place, especially in the view to respond to the request of European Union to produce bioenergy as much as possible from biomass residues. In this regard, several research projects have been funded by EU in the last decade for finding the way to quantify and valorize these products.

Based on Eurostat data for cultivated area for 2013, about 121 million tonnes per year of biomass could have been produced by agricultural crop residues [8].

However, even if the amount of agricultural residues is high, its energetic valorization present a series of problem such as the capacity to collect, the physical and chemical characteristics, the need of pre-processing and the transport costs [9].

An example of residue difficult to be valorized is the "chaff fraction" deriving from the harvest of cereals such as wheat and barley. This fraction consists of the crop

residues from the cleaning shoe of the combine harvester.

Included components are chaff, short straw, leaves, rachis, weed seeds etc. This residue commonly named chaff is left in the field after the passage of the straw baler and is buried with the new tillage. The recovery of the chaff with the current available technology is complicated by the fact that the material is very light and small. This implies the need to identify efficient solutions to address the chaff collection, making the material available for bio-energy valorization at affordable costs.

Within the objectives of the project AGROinLOG funded by EU (<http://agroinlog-h2020.eu/en/home/>), the CREA IT in collaboration with RISE have evaluated the efficiency of a system to incorporate the chaff into the straw flow escaping from the combine during wheat threshing, with the goal to collect the chaff and straw together for the bio-ethanol production in Sweden. This paper displays the results of the first year testing performed in the Scandinavian country.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Pre-harvest measurements

This activity ran in the last week of August 2017 in the province of Uppsala (Sweden) in a flat field of wheat Julius variety. Once arrived in the area, a rectangular field portion of about 3 ha has been delimited with signage sticks to be utilized for the test. The crop characteristics were recorded using 1 m² plots and following a completely randomized design; in total 12 sample areas of 1 m² corresponding to 12 m² have been plotted. Field edges were excluded from the plotting to avoid mistakes due to the "edge effect" (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: scheme of the completely randomized design for plotting the wheat field

The biomass from each plot has been collected in form of whole plants, kept separated. Successively, in a temporary station at the field edge, the stems have been manually separated from the ears; then the ears of each plot were sent to laboratory and threshed using a lab thresher model CICORIA plot 2375 to separate the kernels from chaff and rachis. The kernels were weighed apart, while the remaining biomass fractions were oven dried at 105 °C until they reached constant weight; this procedure allowed determining the dry matter yield of each ligno-cellulosic fraction (straw, chaff, rachis) present in the field.

2.2 Harvest measurements

The combine utilized for the harvest test was a hybrid Fendt 9490 X with head AGCO Power Flow 9.2 m (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Combine harvester Fendt 9490X on work

On the rear part of the combine, the Swedish manufacturer Rekordverken has provided a system, named "Combi" with the objective to allow the management of straw and chaff together or separately, allowing the spreading or the collection of the product according to farmer needs. Basically, the system consists in the association of an appositely designed chaff spreader with the straw chopper of the combine: by changing the settings of the chaff spreader or the straw chopper, four possible work combinations are obtainable as schematized in the figure 3.

Figure 3: possible work combinations (A,B,C,D) obtainable with the "Combi" system.

The work combinations can be explained as follows:

- A) Straw chopper deactivated / chaff spreader in admixing mode: unloading of the straw in the swath for the subsequent baling together with the chaff, which is thrown by the chaff spreader into the straw flow;
- B) Straw chopper deactivated / chaff spreader in spreading mode: the straw is windrowed but chaff is spread over the entire working width of the machine instead of be mixed into the straw flow.
- C) Straw chopper activated / chaff spreader in admixing mode: straw and chaff go together inside the straw chopper and are spread over the entire working width of the machine.
- D) Straw chopper activated / chaff spreader in spreading mode: straw is chopped and spread and chaff is spread separately over the entire width of the machine.

In this test the evaluation was performed with the straw chopper deactivated to allow the formation of the straw swath. On the other hand, the chaff spreader was tested in A modality (admixing) and in B modality (spreading). The goal of the study was to see if the harvest performed with the chaff spreader activated in modality A would have permitted the collection of the chaff with standard baling. Therefore, the material windrowed using the two configurations was successively baled and weighed separately to evaluate the collection efficiency.

The machinery tests were performed in the plotted field following a randomized block design according the following scheme (Fig.4):

Figure 4: experimental design adopted for machinery testing

In each experimental unit, the performances of the machine have been evaluated through the study of the working times according to the protocol C.I.O.S.T.A. CIOSTA (Commission Internationale de l'Organisation du Travail en Agriculture) and adopting the terminology included in the standards ASAE S495 DEC99 [10]. It must be stressed that parameters such as field speed and fuel consumption were obtained directly from the computer

board of the combine, which was reset at the beginning of the harvest operation in each experimental unit.

The combine was tested in both configuration A and B to verify if the activation of the chaff spreader would have interfered with machine efficiency and with the fuel consumption. On the other hand, the baling performance were evaluated to verify if the presence of chaff in the swath would have influenced the field capacity of the tractor + baler.

2.3 Post-harvest measurements

The post harvest measurements can be referred to the product losses, i.e. the biomass left in the field after baling. In this regard, losses of biomass were due to the following reasons: i) straw losses due to the cutting height of the combine (physiological losses); ii) losses of biomass due to the harvest systems.

The straw losses due to cutting height of the combine were evaluated calculating the biomass partitioning along the stem of the plant and measuring the cutting height of the combine. For the biomass partitioning along the stem, 10 samples of 10 stems each were sectioned in portions of 10 cm and weighed with a precision scale. A mean value of biomass portion for each 10 cm of stem was obtained. On the other the cutting height was evaluated as the mean of 100 measurements performed in the field using a manual tape.

The exact amount of material lost was obtained by proportioning the total amount of straw present in the field (calculated with plots) for the percentage of straw left in the field.

Regarding the losses due to harvest system, two methodologies (Fig.5) were used and compared to validate each other's:

- 1) Biomass losses obtained by calculating the difference between residues actually available per unit of surface (identified with plot analysis) and residues effectively collected per unit of surface (bales).
- 2) Biomass losses evaluated as the average of the residues collected with a vacuum system in 3 transects of 9,2m x 0,5m and proportioned to the unit of surface (only in units A).

It must be stressed that losses for practical reasons were not differentiated per plant portion, but they are provided on the base of a total measurement.

Figure 5: weighing of the bales per each experimental unit (1); vacuum bin for the collection of residues in transect, the straw was collected by hand (2).

2.4 Statistical analysis

The Analysis of variance (95% conf. level) was used to evaluate the presence of significant differences among the following experimental factors:

- Combine performances in experimental units A vs. B
- Amount of biomass baled per hectare using configuration A vs. B
- Comparison between methods for losses estimations (method 1 vs. 2)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the pre-harvest field characterization, the plots revealed that the total amount of biomass per hectare was equal to 13,5 tons, of which the 50,7% was grains (6,8 tons*ha⁻¹) the 36,8% was straw (5 tons*ha⁻¹) and the 12,5% was threshing residue (1,7 tons*ha⁻¹) (Fig. 6).

Plant biomass partitioning (%)

Figure 6: graph of the wheat biomass partitioning

A calculation based on three replicated samples of the material threshed revealed that the rachis was the 7% of the total threshing residues, while the remaining was grain chaff.

Regarding the machinery test, the combine exhibited a very good field capacity and no significant differences were identified in the performances using configuration A or B. On the other hand, the field efficiency could be even higher in normal Swedish work conditions because turning would be reduced for the great extension of the agricultural fields (Table I).

Table I: combine performance in the 6 exp. units

Combine: FENDT 9490X				
Plot	Theor. field capacity	Eff. field capacity	Field efficiency	Fuel cons.
	ha/h	ha/h	%	l/h
A1	4,7	2,9	62%	10
B1	4,5	2,7	61%	
B2	5,6	3,3	59%	10,6
A2	5,7	3,4	59%	10
B3	5,8	3,2	56%	9,7
A3	4,7	3,0	65%	

The performance of the tractor + balers are presented in the table below (table II).

Table II: performance of the baling yard

Tractor: New Holland T6.175 + Baler: New Holland roll baler 125 Combi				
Plot	Theor. field capacity	Eff. field capacity	Field efficiency	Mat. capacity
	ha/h	ha/h	%	t/h
A1	4,4	1,5	35%	4,01
B1	4,4	2,0	45%	5,69
B2	3,8	1,1	29%	3,29
A2	3,8	1,8	49%	4,27
B3	3,9	2,1	53%	5,17
A3	3,2	1,4	44%	3,23

In this case the results show a very low field efficiency, mainly due to repeated machinery stops caused by the clogging of the machine.

In this regard, it must be stressed that the straw produced by the hybrid combine harvesters is in general shorter respect that produced with traditional combines and conventional balers have a scarce attitude to wrap such a short product.

The decision of using a hybrid combine in this test was partly due to the fact that this type of combine is very popular now in northern Europe because of their high capacity in cereal seeds. Of interest in this context is also that the hybrid combines create relatively large amounts of material to the cleaning shoe of the combine harvester. i.e. the chaff fraction is extensive.

Regarding the biomass losses due to cutting height, the measurements revealed that the mean cutting height was 16,2 cm corresponding to the 29% of the total straw available. Considering the amount of straw (d.m. basis) was 5 tons per hectare, the amount of material lost due to cutting height corresponded to 1,45 tons (Fig.7).

This study implies that the amount of straw available for baling was in reality 3,55 tons of dry matter per hectare. Therefore, in experimental units A, the theoretically amount of biomass available for baling was 5,25 tons per hectare (3,55 tons of straw + 1,7 tons of chaff and rachis), while in experimental units B the amount was less than that because the chaff spreader was in the spreading mode. The bales weighing revealed that the amount of biomass baled in units A was 2,77 tons per hectare while in units B was 2,43 tons per hectare.

Statistical analysis revealed that the material collected in A was significantly higher than that in B.

However, losses were extensive for both treatments accounted in 47,3% in units A and 31,6% in units B. In must be noted that in B the losses result lower because the 1,7 tons of chaff + rachis are not considered as collectable material; therefore the 31,6% losses is referred only for the straw fraction.

Figure 7: straw partitioning along the stems. Different colors indicate sections of 10 cm.

The study of the losses performed with the methodology 2 revealed that losses in units A were equal to 2,33 tons per hectare and confirmed the results obtained with methodology 1. Statistical analysis showed no significant differences among the methods validating each other's (Fig.8).

Figure 8: difference between the area vacuumed and non-vacuumed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study revealed that the chaff spreader in admixing mode allowed to collect 14% more material respect the configuration with the chaff spreader in spreading mode, but although losses were close to 50%. The problems identified can be principally attributed to the use of a hybrid combine harvester, which produced a relatively short straw short and therefore difficult to be baled. The validity of the system will be verified in the next future, probably testing other machinery and equipment, performing a similar experiment.

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6 REFERENCES

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7 LOGO SPACE

